

From turbulence to cosmic structure: a unified theory for Kolmogorov spectrum, halo mass function, and halo density profile

Zhijie (Jay) Xu,^{1*}

¹Physical and Computational Sciences Directorate, Pacific Northwest National Laboratory; Richland, WA 99354, USA

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ABSTRACT

We develop a unified stochastic framework for a broad class of nonequilibrium systems and apply it to turbulence and cosmic structure formation. Spectra and distributions in these systems are modeled as transport processes in an appropriate “scale space”, described by random walks and Fokker–Planck equations with scale-dependent waiting times. Reformulating the turbulent cascade as a random walk in wavenumber space with a k -dependent waiting time, we recover the Kolmogorov $-5/3$ law and obtain the full energy spectrum including the inertial-dissipation crossover, exponential cutoff, and spectrum constant without invoking dimensional arguments. For a bottom-up hierarchical halo structure formation, low-mass haloes collapse early and retain strong primordial imprints, while prolonged assembly of large haloes near characteristic mass m_h^* tends to erase this memory and establishes a universal spectrum. We model this process as an analogous random walk of dark matter haloes in mass space m_h with a mass-dependent waiting time $\tau_g \propto m_h^{-\lambda}$. The model yields a stretched Gaussian halo mass function that reproduces the Press–Schechter form, with both small-scale scaling $f_M \propto m_h^{-\lambda}$ and exponential cutoff at $m_h > m_h^*$ set by exponent λ . The framework naturally produces a double- λ mass function, where λ reflects primordial spectrum at low masses and approaches $\lambda=2/3$ near m_h^* where gravity dominates. For individual haloes, a spatial random walk with waiting time $\tau_{gr} \propto r^{-\gamma}$ generates a double- γ density profile that reproduces the Einasto profile, with both small-scale scaling $\rho_r \propto r^{-2\gamma}$ and exponential cutoff at $r > r_s$ set by exponent γ . In this case, γ is fixed by the initial spectrum in the inner regions and approaches $\gamma=2/3$ in the outer regions and for haloes near m_h^* . Our results demonstrate that this simple stochastic framework provides a common theoretical description of both turbulent cascades and cosmic structure formation.

Key words: Turbulence; Energy spectrum; Dark matter; Mass function; Halo density;

1 INTRODUCTION

Turbulence plays a central role in modern astrophysics. Most astrophysical plasmas and gases are neither laminar nor static. From the interstellar medium (ISM) to galaxy clusters, accretion disks around compact objects, and stars, turbulent flows are ubiquitous, typically highly compressible, magnetized, and driven far from equilibrium [1, 2, 3]. In such environments, the detailed microphysics is often poorly constrained, but the large-scale dynamics are dominated by cascades of energy across many orders of magnitude in scale. Turbulence theory provides the natural framework for describing this multiscale transfer of energy, momentum, and magnetic helicity.

Because microphysics is usually uncertain or inaccessible, astrophysics relies heavily on the idea of universal turbulent spectra. Kolmogorov’s $-5/3$ law and its MHD extensions provide key relations between the mean energy flux and the distribution of energy in wavenumber (k) space. If the spectrum is universal and dependent only on a few macroscopic parameters, one can extrapolate from laboratory experiments and numerical simulations to regimes far beyond terrestrial conditions. These considerations motivate the search for a universal spectrum not only for ordinary baryonic turbulence but also for more exotic sectors. If dark matter, for example, undergoes some form of mass/energy transfer through gravitational clustering, one

may ask whether its distribution and structure tend toward a universal form analogous to the Kolmogorov spectrum, manifested in universal halo mass functions and density profiles [4, 5]. Establishing such universality would provide a powerful bridge between microphysical dark matter models and macroscopic cosmological observables.

Nonlinear nonequilibrium systems in both fluid dynamics and cosmology exhibit a remarkably similar phenomenology: strongly self-interacting many-body dynamics give rise to robust, nearly universal spectra and distributions when viewed in an appropriate “scale space”. Turbulent flows provide the canonical example. At high Reynolds number, energy injected at large scales L cascades through a hierarchy of eddies toward small scales, where it is dissipated at dissipation scale η . In the classical Kolmogorov (K41) framework, intermediate inertial-range scales are assumed to be statistically homogeneous, isotropic, and self-similar, and to be governed solely by the mean energy flux ε through scales. Under these assumptions, the dimensional analysis leads to the celebrated Kolmogorov $-5/3$ spectrum [6]. Outside the inertial range, viscous effects determine the spectral shape, and empirical “bridge” functions are commonly employed to smoothly interpolate between the inertial- and dissipation-range behavior. A widely used empirical spectrum often takes the form (Pao spectrum [7])

$$E(k) = C_K \varepsilon^{2/3} k^{-5/3} \exp \left[-\frac{3}{2} C_K (\eta k)^{4/3} \right], \quad (1)$$

* E-mail: zhijie.xu@pnl.gov; zhijie.xu@hotmail.com

where η is the Kolmogorov microscale and C_K is a universal constant of value 1.5 to 1.7. Thus, despite the complexity of the Navier–Stokes dynamics, the energy spectrum assumes a simple, nearly universal form: a $-5/3$ power law with an exponential cutoff at large k , set primarily by the mean dissipation rate and only weakly dependent on the details of the initial forcing. Nevertheless, deriving such a universal spectrum from first principles, using only exact conservation and transfer relations, without recourse to dimensional arguments or phenomenological closures, remains an outstanding theoretical problem and provides the primary motivation for the present work.

Remarkably similar issues also arise in the nonlinear evolution of collisionless dark matter. Gravitational collapse produces highly localized, virialized haloes that are the fundamental building blocks of large-scale structures [8]. Their number density as a function of mass is encoded in the halo mass function, while their internal structure is described by halo density profiles. The Press–Schechter approach and its generalizations model halo formation as a first-crossing problem, in which a stochastic trajectory in smoothed density space crosses a critical collapse barrier [9, 10]. Subsequent extensions to correlated random walks further refined this framework [11, 12, 13]. The resulting Press–Schechter (PS) mass function closely parallels the turbulence energy spectrum $E(k)$ in Eq. (1), exhibiting a power-law behaviour at low masses, controlled by the effective spectral index n , and an exponential cutoff at a mass M^* ,

$$f_{PS}(m_h) = \frac{3+n}{3\sqrt{2\pi}} \frac{1}{M^*} \left(\frac{m_h}{M^*}\right)^{-\frac{3+n}{6}} \exp\left[-\frac{1}{2}\left(\frac{m_h}{M^*}\right)^{\frac{3+n}{3}}\right], \quad (2)$$

where m_h is the mass of haloes. Despite providing a remarkably simple analytic estimate of halo abundances, the PS mass function relies on highly idealized assumptions, most notably spherical collapse and a fixed critical overdensity δ_c , thereby motivating alternative perspectives in this paper.

The near-universal halo density profile from highly nonlinear gravitational dynamics poses another problem closely analogous to the appearance of universal spectrum in turbulence. Over a wide range of halo masses and cosmological models, numerical simulations show that the spherically averaged density profiles are well described by the Einasto form, which again features a flat slope at small r and an exponential cutoff as Eqs. (1) and (2) [14, 15, 16, 17]

$$\rho_h^{ES}(r) = \rho_s \exp\left(\frac{2}{\alpha}\right) \exp\left[-\frac{2}{\alpha}\left(\frac{r}{r_s}\right)^\alpha\right], \quad (3)$$

where ρ_s is the density at scale radius r_s . The shape parameter α varies weakly with mass and redshift, indicating a robust, approximately self-similar structure across haloes of different scales [18]. Despite intensive study, there is currently no first-principle theory that uniquely predicts the density profile and the physical meaning of α , which also motivates the present work.

These parallels motivate a unified viewpoint in which three seemingly distinct problems (Eqs. (1), (2), and (3)) can be treated within a common framework. Because the dark component is collisionless, it does not support turbulent cascades driven by viscous dissipation and vortex; similarly, a halo that has reached full virial equilibrium cannot sustain a net transfer of mass or energy across spatial scales. Consequently, we acknowledge the difference between three problems and focus on the scale-to-scale redistribution of mass and energy in self-gravitating dark matter, rather than a viscous Kolmogorov-type cascade for dark matter.

The unified framework employs random-walk or diffusion models in an appropriate “scale space”. In this view, the “cascade” or “scale-to-scale” mass or energy transfer is formulated as a stochastic transport process in that scale space. Using the turbulence energy

Figure 1. Schematic depiction of a random walk in wavenumber k space underlying the turbulence energy spectrum. Energy is injected at the integral scale k_L (or equivalently L in real space), represented by a delta-like distribution of a group of “energy carriers”, each carrying an infinitesimal energy dE . The dominant local triadic interactions ($\mathbf{k}+\mathbf{p}+\mathbf{q}=0$) transfer “energy carriers” (blue dots) from a wavenumber k to a nearby wavenumber $k+\delta k$, producing a step-wise random walk toward larger k (red arrows). Each step conserves total energy, while the waiting time $\tau_{gk}(k)$ between steps depends on k and encodes the finite lifetime of eddies at that scale. In the stationary state, the resulting distribution $P(k)$ of “energy carriers” is proportional to the energy spectrum $E(k)$, shown here as a Kolmogorov $-5/3$ law with an exponential cutoff near the dissipation wavenumber k_η (or η in real space), where viscous effects dominate and remove energy.

spectrum as an example (Fig. 1), the “cascade” is driven by local triad interactions and constrained by exact energy conservation. The energy spectrum is interpreted as the distribution of “energy carriers” carrying an infinitesimal energy dE and executing a random walk in k -space, with a scale-dependent waiting time $\tau_{gk}(k)$ that reflects the nonlinear eddy turnaround time. The stationary solution of the corresponding Fokker–Planck equation in k -space, with viscous dissipation acting as a scale-dependent sink (Eq. (8)), yields the entire energy spectrum. This simple framework recovers the Kolmogorov $-5/3$ law, predicts the exponential dissipation-range cutoff, and fixes the spectrum constant C_K . A constant mean energy flux ε through scales is not an a priori assumption but emerges from the dynamics.

In what follows, we apply this random-walk framework to three seemingly distinct problems: (i) the turbulence energy cascade as a random walk in wavenumber space, yielding the Kolmogorov $-5/3$ scaling and the entire energy spectrum; (ii) hierarchical halo assembly as a random walk in halo mass space m_h , yielding the halo mass function; and (iii) particle migration within haloes as a random walk in space \mathbf{x} , shaping the halo density profile. In each case, the underlying many-body dynamics are described as stochastic evolution in an appropriate “scale space”. Universal spectra or distributions naturally emerge as stationary or time-dependent solutions. We develop this perspective systematically, constructing random-walk models in each “scale space”, and demonstrate how this unified framework can account for the observed universality of turbulence spectra, halo mass function, and density profiles.

2 RANDOM WALK IN K-SPACE FOR TURBULENCE

Kolmogorov’s $-5/3$ scaling is derived under the assumption that, at sufficiently high Reynolds numbers, small-scale turbulence is statistically homogeneous and isotropic and is characterized solely by a scale-independent mean energy dissipation rate ε and the kinematic viscosity ν . In the inertial range, between k_L and k_η (Fig. 1), energy is transferred conservatively across scales. Dimensional analysis then

implies a universal energy spectrum $E(k) = C_K \varepsilon^{2/3} k^{-5/3}$ over this range. In the following, we show that the energy cascade can instead be formulated as a random walk process in wavenumber space, from which the $-5/3$ scaling, the full spectral shape, and the spectrum constant C_K emerge naturally without invoking dimensional arguments and a scale-independent rate of dissipation ε .

We first normalize the steady state energy spectrum to obtain a probability density $P(k)$ in wavenumber space. The total kinetic energy per unit mass satisfies

$$\int_0^\infty E(k) dk = \frac{1}{2} u_0^2, \quad (4)$$

where u_0 is the characteristic velocity at the integral scale L . We then define the distribution function $P(k)$

$$P(k) = 2E(k)/u_0^2 \quad \text{such that} \quad \int_0^\infty P(k) dk = 1, \quad (5)$$

$$N(k) = P(k)k = 2E(k)k/u_0^2.$$

Here, $P(k) \propto E(k)$ is the energy spectrum normalized by the total energy, and $N(k)$ can be viewed as the probability (or number fraction) associated with the scale k .

To model the cascade, we interpret $P(k)$ as the distribution of fictitious particles X in k -space, each carrying an infinitesimal energy $dE = u_0^2/2N$ with total number of particles $N \rightarrow \infty$. The nonlinear energy transfer is represented as a one-dimensional continuous-time random walk of these particles: a local jump of X from $k \rightarrow k + \delta k$ corresponds to transferring the infinitesimal energy dE from $k \rightarrow k + \delta k$ due to a local triad interaction at scale k (Fig. 1). In direct analogy with ordinary diffusion, where spatial random walks generate the evolution of particle density, $P(k,t)$ describes the temporal evolution of the energy distribution in k -space, with a stationary spectrum $P(k)$. This construction naturally incorporates four key properties of the cascade:

(i) **Scale-locality.** The energy flux at wavenumber k is assumed to be dominated by local triadic interactions among three modes with $|\mathbf{k}| \sim |\mathbf{p}| \sim |\mathbf{q}|$, while strongly nonlocal interactions are subleading [19, 20]. In the random-walk picture, this is implemented by restricting particles moving only between neighboring shells (k to $k+\delta k$) and energy is transferred only between adjacent scales.

(ii) **Energy conservation.** All triadic interactions are energy-conserving. In the absence of forcing and dissipation, the total number of particles is conserved. Since each particle carries an infinitesimal energy dE , the stochastic dynamics merely redistributes energy in k -space without changing the total energy, implementing conservative transfer across the entire range.

(iii) **Viscous dissipation.** Viscosity removes kinetic energy at a rate of $2\nu k^2 E(k)$. Translating this into the particle picture produces a scale-dependent sink term $2\nu k^2 P(k)$ (Eq. (8)), which represents the loss of particles (and hence energy) from the shell k due to the viscous damping of modes k . The k^2 dependence reflects the Laplacian in the Navier–Stokes equations and ensures that dissipation is negligible at large scales and dominant on small scales.

(iv) **Scale-dependent waiting time.** The waiting time $\tau_{gk}(k)$ between successive steps for each X particle is identified with the characteristic lifetime $\tau_k(k)$ of eddies at scale k . In Kolmogorov phenomenology, this lifetime is a power law of k , and, without loss of generality, we parameterize it as $\tau_{gk}(k) \propto k^{-\gamma}$ with $\gamma > 0$. This captures the fact that smaller-scale eddies (larger k) interact and decorre-

late more rapidly, and it provides a minimal parametrization of possible deviations from the Kolmogorov scaling when intermittency or additional physics are included. The exponent γ will be determined self-consistently below.

We consider an idealized initial condition in which all X particles are concentrated at $k=0$, corresponding to energy injection exclusively at the largest scales ($k_L=0$). In this limit, there is no distinct energy-containing range and only the universal equilibrium range is relevant. The subsequent evolution of the particle distribution in k -space is modeled as a one-dimensional continuous-time random walk with a position-dependent residence (waiting) time $\tau_{gk}(k)$. The corresponding Langevin equation in k -space reads

$$\frac{dk_t}{dt} = \sqrt{2D_P(k_t)} \xi(t) \propto \frac{\delta k}{\tau_{gk}} \propto \frac{\delta k}{k^{-\gamma}}, \quad (6)$$

where $\xi(t)$ is Gaussian white noise. Here, $\delta k/\tau_{gk}(k)$ denotes the average rate of change of k_t . We assume a power-law scaling $\tau_{gk}(k) \propto k^{-\gamma}$, implying a position-dependent k -space diffusivity

$$D_P(k_t) = D_0 k^{2\gamma}, \quad (7)$$

where D_0 is a proportional constant. Thus, smaller k corresponds to reduced k -space diffusivity and consequently a longer waiting time.

The evolution of the particle distribution $P(k,t)$ in wavenumber space is governed by the corresponding Fokker–Planck equation

$$\frac{\partial P(k,t)}{\partial t} = \underbrace{\frac{\partial}{\partial k} \left[\alpha \frac{\partial D_P}{\partial k} P + D_P \frac{\partial P}{\partial k} \right]}_1 - \underbrace{2\nu k^2 P}_2, \quad (8)$$

where the first term represents energy transfer in k -space generated by the Langevin Eq. (6), with a position-dependent diffusivity $D_P(k)$ and an interpretation parameter α specifying the stochastic calculus ($\alpha=1$ for Itô, $\alpha=1/2$ for Stratonovich [21], and other values determined by the underlying microphysics). The second term describes viscous dissipation, leading to a k -dependent decay of X population.

The exact steady state solution of Eq. (8) reads (Appendix A)

$$P(k) = Ak^{-(1+\gamma)} \exp \left[-\sqrt{\frac{2\nu}{D_0}} \left(\frac{k^{2-\gamma}}{2-\gamma} \right) \right] \\ = Ak^{-(1+\gamma)} \exp \left[-\lambda \left(k/k_\eta \right)^{2-\gamma} \right], \quad (9)$$

where A is a proportional constant and the stochastic interpretation parameter should be $\alpha = (1 + 1/\gamma)/2$. Identifying $P(k)$ with the energy spectrum, we obtain an inertial-range scaling $E(k) \propto k^{-(1+\gamma)}$ at small k , controlled by the waiting-time exponent γ , together with an inertial-dissipation crossover described by an exponential cut-off $\exp(-k^{2-\gamma})$. We introduce a characteristic wavenumber k_η that marks the onset of exponential decay for $k > k_\eta$. This allows us to define the dimensionless parameter λ

$$\lambda = \sqrt{\frac{2\nu}{D_0}} \frac{k_\eta^{2-\gamma}}{2-\gamma}. \quad (10)$$

The n th moment of the distribution $P(k)$ can be easily found as

$$\int_{k_L}^\infty P(k) k^n dk = \frac{A k_\eta^{n-\gamma}}{(2-\gamma) \lambda^{\frac{n-\gamma}{2-\gamma}}} \Gamma \left(\frac{n-\gamma}{2-\gamma}, \lambda \left(\frac{k_L}{k_\eta} \right)^{2-\gamma} \right), \quad (11)$$

where k_L denotes the integral wavenumber scale. Here, $\Gamma(x, y)$ is the upper incomplete Gamma function with limits

$$\lim_{y \rightarrow 0} \Gamma(x, y) = \Gamma(x) - y^x/x \quad \text{and} \quad \lim_{y \rightarrow \infty} \Gamma(x, y) = 0 \quad (12)$$

The constant A is obtained by imposing $\int_{k_L \rightarrow 0}^{\infty} P(k) dk = 1$ (zeroth moment with $n=0$ in Eq. (11)),

$$A = \frac{(2-\gamma)\lambda^{-\frac{\gamma}{2-\gamma}} k_L^\gamma}{\Gamma\left(-\frac{\gamma}{2-\gamma}, \lambda\left(\frac{k_L}{k_\eta}\right)^{2-\gamma}\right)} \approx \frac{\gamma k_L^\gamma}{1 + \frac{\gamma}{2-\gamma} \Gamma\left(-\frac{\gamma}{2-\gamma}\right) \lambda^{\frac{\gamma}{2-\gamma}} \left(\frac{k_L}{k_\eta}\right)^\gamma} \quad (13)$$

and for $k_L \ll k_\eta$, simplifies to $A \approx \gamma k_L^\gamma$. In this limit ($k_L \rightarrow 0$), the distribution finally reduces to

$$P(k) = \frac{2E(k)}{u_0^2} = \gamma k_L^\gamma k^{-(1+\gamma)} \exp\left[-\lambda\left(\frac{k}{k_\eta}\right)^{2-\gamma}\right]. \quad (14)$$

The integral and dissipation wavenumbers, k_L and k_η , are related to the corresponding real-space integral scale L and dissipative scale η by a constant $\beta = 1/2\pi$,

$$\eta = 1/(\beta k_\eta) \quad \text{and} \quad L = 1/(\beta k_L). \quad (15)$$

We next introduce the standard spectral kinetic energy flux function $\Pi_E(k)$ defined as the net transfer of energy from all modes smaller than k to all modes larger than k . Using $E(k)$ in Eq. (14), the flux can be written as

$$\begin{aligned} \Pi_E(k) &= \int_k^\infty 2\nu E(k') k'^2 dk' \\ &= \frac{\gamma \nu u_0^2 k_\eta^2}{(2-\gamma)\lambda} \left(\frac{k_L}{k_\eta}\right)^\gamma \exp\left[-\lambda\left(\frac{k}{k_\eta}\right)^{2-\gamma}\right] \end{aligned} \quad (16)$$

and is related to the spectrum $E(k)$ through

$$\Pi_E(k) = \frac{2\nu}{(2-\gamma)\lambda} k_\eta^{2-\gamma} k^{1+\gamma} E(k). \quad (17)$$

The mean dissipation rate ε follows from flux in the limit $k \rightarrow 0$,

$$\begin{aligned} \varepsilon = \Pi_E(k \rightarrow 0) &= \frac{\gamma \nu u_0^2}{(2-\gamma)\lambda} k_L^\gamma k_\eta^{2-\gamma} \\ &= \frac{\gamma}{2-\gamma} \frac{1}{\lambda \beta^2} \left(\frac{u_0^{2/\gamma}}{L}\right)^\gamma \left(\frac{u_\eta^{1/(1-\gamma)}}{\eta}\right)^{1-\gamma}, \end{aligned} \quad (18)$$

where $u_\eta = \nu/\eta$ is the characteristic velocity at scale η .

We have so far characterized the turbulence spectrum in terms of a scale-dependent waiting time $\tau_{gk} \propto k^{-\gamma}$ with an a priori unknown exponent γ . To fix γ , we invoke a simple physical argument. For a spectrum $E(k) \propto k^{-(1+\gamma)}$, the energy associated with wavenumber k scales as $u_k^2 \propto E(k)k \propto k^{-\gamma}$, so that the characteristic eddy velocity satisfies $u_k \propto k^{-\gamma/2}$. The corresponding eddy-turnover time is then $\tau_k \propto (u_k k)^{-1} \propto k^{\gamma/2-1}$. In our random-walk picture, the transfer of an infinitesimal energy element dE from k to $k + \delta k$ is mediated by local triadic interactions, whose characteristic time is precisely τ_k . Thus the waiting time must satisfy $\tau_{gk} \propto \tau_k \propto k^{\gamma/2-1}$. Consistency with the assumed scaling $\tau_{gk} \propto k^{-\gamma}$ requires

$$\frac{\gamma}{2} - 1 = -\gamma \quad \text{such that} \quad \gamma = 2/3. \quad (19)$$

With $\gamma = 2/3$, Eq. (14) reproduces the Kolmogorov $-5/3$ spectrum together with an exponential cutoff $\exp(-k^{4/3})$ across the inertial-dissipation transition. The dissipation rate in Eq. (18) becomes

$$\varepsilon = \frac{1}{2\lambda\beta^2} \left(\frac{u_0^3}{L}\right)^{2/3} \left(\frac{u_\eta^3}{\eta}\right)^{1/3}. \quad (20)$$

Since the rate of energy dissipation is finite, this requires $L \propto u_0^3$ with the limit $k_L \rightarrow 0$ or $L \rightarrow \infty$. For $\gamma = 2/3$, the velocity $u_k \propto k^{-\gamma/2} \propto k^{-1/3}$ and $u_k^3 k$ is a constant. This is equivalent to a relation $u_0^3/L \sim$

$u_k^3/l \sim u_\eta^3/\eta$ for scales $\eta < l < L$, where u_k is the characteristic velocity at wavenumber k or scale l in real space. We now choose a constant C_X and the scale η to satisfy an exact relation

$$\varepsilon = C_X \frac{u_0^3}{L} = \frac{u_\eta^3}{\eta} \quad \text{and} \quad C_X^{2/3} \cdot 2\lambda\beta^2 = 1, \quad (21)$$

where C_X is a numerical constant on the order of one. With Eq. (21) and $u_\eta = \nu/\eta$, the Kolmogorov microscales naturally emerge as $\eta = (\nu^3/\varepsilon)^{1/4}$ from this equation.

Using Eqs. (14) and (21), the full equilibrium-range spectrum and the Kolmogorov constant C_K are

$$\begin{aligned} E(k) &= C_K \varepsilon^{2/3} k^{-5/3} \exp\left[-\frac{3}{2} C_K (\eta k)^{4/3}\right], \\ C_K &= \frac{1}{3} (\beta C_X)^{-2/3} \quad \text{and} \quad \lambda = \frac{3}{2} C_K \beta^{-4/3}. \end{aligned} \quad (22)$$

Thus, the empirical Pao spectrum in Eq. (1) is analytically recovered without invoking any additional assumptions in the original derivation [7], with $C_K \approx 1.6$ for $C_X = 0.6$. In this framework, a random walk of energy-carrying particles in wavenumber space, driven by local triadic interactions, suffices to reproduce the complete equilibrium energy spectrum, suggesting a promising avenue for extensions to MHD turbulence and intermittency. In the following sections, the same approach is extended to cosmic structure formation.

3 HALO RANDOM WALK FOR MASS FUNCTION

For collisionless dark matter, long-range gravity favors the formation of a broad halo mass spectrum that maximizes the entropy of the self-gravitating system [22]. Haloes act as the basic elements of the dark matter flow—analogous to eddies in turbulence—mediating the transfer of mass across scales, with their abundance encoded in the halo mass function. As illustrated in Fig. 2, hierarchical structure formation can be viewed as a random walk in mass space: the merger of a halo of mass M with a single infalling mass m (smooth accretion, set by the mass resolution or particle mass) produces a halo of mass $M + m$, thereby generating a continuous flux of mass toward larger masses. For haloes of mass m_h , such merger events occur on average after a waiting time $\tau_g(m_h)$, so that haloes continuously grow through successive smooth accretion events.

The halo mass distribution is controlled by both the primordial conditions and subsequent gravitational evolution. In the Press-Schechter framework, the mass function scales as $\propto m_h^{-\frac{n-3}{6}}$, depending only on the spectral index n (Eq. (2)). In hierarchical structure formation, low-mass haloes collapse at early times from peaks of the initial density field, so their abundance largely reflects the statistics of these peaks and preserves a strong memory of the primordial power spectrum. By contrast, massive haloes form later through a sequence of mergers and continuous accretion, and this extended, nonlinear assembly tends to erase details of the initial conditions. As a result, the mass function near the characteristic mass m_h^* is expected to be quasi-universal, determined primarily by gravitational dynamics and only weakly dependent on the initial spectral shape. To derive a general form of halo mass function, we assume a power-law form $\tau_g \propto m_h^{-\lambda}$, where the effective exponent λ is set by either the initial power spectrum or gravitational dynamics, depending on which dominates.

We adopt an idealized initial condition in which the halo population is sharply localized at $m_h=0$ in mass space (Fig. 2), representing the nearly simultaneous formation of a very large number of small, high-density proto-haloes at high redshift throughout the universe. The subsequent evolution of the halo distribution in mass

Figure 2. Schematic plot for the halo random walk in halo mass space. A halo of mass M that merges with a single free particle of mass m undergoes a step to the next mass scale $M + m$, representing a smooth accretion and a net mass flux toward larger halo masses. For a halo of mass m_h , such mergers occur with an average waiting time $\tau_g(m_h)$. Starting from sharply localized initial conditions, this stochastic process generates a distribution of haloes in mass space, with the corresponding halo mass function determined by the associated Fokker-Planck equation.

space is modeled as a continuous-time random walk with a mass-dependent waiting time $\tau_g(m_h)$. The stochastic evolution in mass space then yields the halo mass function as a solution of the associated Fokker-Planck equation. This construction does not invoke any specific collapse model (spherical or ellipsoidal), is mathematically tractable, and differs fundamentally from the Press-Schechter formalism, thereby providing complementary insight into the origin and evolution of the halo mass function.

The stochastic growth of dark matter haloes can be modeled as a random walk in mass space governed by a Langevin equation [4],

$$\frac{\partial m_h(t)}{\partial t} = \sqrt{2D_p(m_h)}\zeta(t) \propto \frac{m}{\tau_g} \propto \frac{m}{m_h^{-\lambda}}, \quad (23)$$

where the Gaussian white noise $\zeta(t)$ satisfies the covariance $\langle \zeta(t)\zeta(t') \rangle = \delta(t-t')$. The waiting time τ_g for a mass-space step is assumed to be scale dependent, $\tau_g \propto m_h^{-\lambda}$, which implies a mass-dependent diffusivity in halo mass space

$$D_p(m_h) = D_{p0}(t)m_h^{2\lambda}, \quad (24)$$

where $D_{p0}(t)$ is a proportional constant.

The corresponding Fokker-Planck equation for the halo mass function $f_M(m_h, t)$ reads

$$\frac{\partial f_M(m_h, t)}{\partial t} = \frac{\partial}{\partial m_h} \left[\alpha \frac{\partial D_p}{\partial m_h} f_M + D_p \frac{\partial f_M}{\partial m_h} \right], \quad (25)$$

where α specifies the interpretation of the stochastic integral.

Equation (25) admits an analytic solution (Appendix A), yielding a stretched-Gaussian mass function with a power-law behavior at low mass and an exponential cut-off at high mass,

$$f_M(m_h, t) = \frac{m_h^{-\lambda}}{\sqrt{\pi D_{p0} t}} \exp \left[-\frac{m_h^{2-2\lambda}}{4(1-\lambda)^2 D_{p0} t} \right]. \quad (26)$$

Solution requires $\alpha=1/2$, corresponding to the Stratonovich's interpretation [23, 24].

The characteristic mass $m_h^*(t)$ is related to the mean square displacement in the mass space as

$$\langle m_h^2 \rangle = \int_0^\infty f_M(m_h, t) m_h^2 dm_h \equiv \gamma_0 m_h^{*2}. \quad (27)$$

where γ_0 is a proportional constant. With m_h^* as the characteristic mass, the halo mass function can be rewritten as

$$f_M(m_h, t) = \frac{(1-\lambda)}{\sqrt{\pi\eta_0} m_h^*} \left(\frac{m_h}{m_h^*} \right)^{-\lambda} \exp \left[-\frac{1}{4\eta_0} \left(\frac{m_h}{m_h^*} \right)^{2-2\lambda} \right], \quad (28)$$

where η_0 is a dimensionless constant. The exponent λ is thus the key parameter determining both the mass-space waiting time $\tau_g \propto m_h^{-\lambda}$ and the slope of the mass function. Comparison with the Press-Schechter mass function (Eq. (2)) shows that λ is related to the power spectrum index n through

$$\lambda = (3-n)/6, \quad (29)$$

so that our solution reduces to the Press-Schechter mass function for $\lambda = (3-n)/6$ and $\eta_0 = 1/2$.

The parameter λ characterizes both the slope of the halo mass function and the associated waiting time (or merging rate) in the random walk picture. A more negative initial spectral index n implies a larger λ and hence less frequent mergers. For a CDM-like spectrum, λ is expected to increase toward unity at lower masses (higher wavenumbers k with $n \rightarrow -3$ from Eq. (29)). Because the small-scale regime is primarily shaped by the primordial power spectrum, whereas the universal regime near m_h^* is governed by gravitational dynamics, it is natural to introduce two effective exponents, λ_1 and λ_2 , describing these distinct ranges. The fully nonlinear small-scale region ($m_h \ll m_h^*$) retains a stronger imprint of the initial spectrum, while scales around m_h^* are dominated by gravity. The single- λ mass function in Eq. (28) can therefore be generalized to a double- λ form [4],

$$f_M(m_h, t) = (2\sqrt{\eta_0})^{-q} \frac{2(1-\lambda_1)}{q\Gamma(q/2)} \cdot \frac{1}{m_h^*} \left(\frac{m_h^*}{m_h} \right)^{\lambda_1} \exp \left[-\frac{1}{4\eta_0} \left(\frac{m_h}{m_h^*} \right)^{2-2\lambda_2} \right], \quad (30)$$

with $q = (1-\lambda_1)/(1-\lambda_2)$. Introducing the dimensionless variable $v = (m_h/m_h^*)^{2-2\lambda_2}$, the corresponding dimensionless double- λ mass function becomes

$$f_{D\lambda}(v) = \frac{(2\sqrt{\eta_0})^{-q}}{\Gamma(q/2)} v^{q/2-1} \exp \left(-\frac{v}{4\eta_0} \right). \quad (31)$$

In this framework one may also define a mass flux Π_m describing scale-to-scale mass transfer and a scale-independent mass transfer rate $\varepsilon_m = \Pi_m(m_h \rightarrow 0)$ [5].

The above mass function is constructed from a general power-law waiting time $\tau_g(m_h) \propto m_h^{-\lambda}$. When the primordial spectrum dominates, λ is related to the initial spectral index (Eq. (29)). In a gravity-dominated regime, τ_g is set by the halo potential (Eq. (37)),

$$\tau_g(m_h) \propto \Phi(m_h)^{-1} \propto \frac{r_h}{Gm_h} \propto m_h^{-\lambda}. \quad (32)$$

More massive haloes have deeper potentials, larger velocity dispersions, and thus shorter residence times and faster mass accretion. With $r_h \propto m_h^{1/3}$, this yields a universal $\lambda = 2/3$, corresponding to an effective spectral index $n=-1$ from Eq. (29).

4 PARTICLE RANDOM WALK FOR HALO STRUCTURE

Similarly to the halo mass function, the internal structure of haloes, i.e. the spatial distribution of dark matter particles, can be described within the same stochastic framework. The halo density profile is also shaped jointly by primordial spectrum and gravitational dynamics. A steeper primordial spectrum (more negative index) generally produces haloes with lower concentrations and less dense central cusps. Because halo assembly proceeds inside–out, the innermost regions collapse earlier from high-redshift peaks in the initial density field; therefore, their structure retains a strong memory of the primordial spectrum. In contrast, the outer halo regions are assembled later through numerous successive mergers and smooth accretion events, which progressively erase the memory of the initial spectrum. Consequently, the dynamics near the characteristic scale radius r_s , and for haloes with a characteristic mass m_h^* , become approximately universal and are governed primarily by gravity, with only a weak dependence on the initial conditions.

To model this behavior, we consider an idealized proto-halo whose entire mass is initially concentrated at $r=0$, representing the collapse of an extreme high-redshift peak of high density. The subsequent evolution is treated as a random walk of dark matter particles in a self-consistent mean gravitational potential determined by the instantaneous particle distribution. The particle trajectories are modeled as a three-dimensional continuous-time random walk with a radius-dependent residence (waiting) time $\tau_{gr}(r)$. We assume a power-law form $\tau_{gr}(r) \propto r^{-\gamma}$, where the exponent γ encodes the influence of the primordial spectrum and/or gravitational dynamics.

The stochastic motion of an individual particle with position X_t is described by the Langevin equation

$$\frac{dX_t}{dt} = \sqrt{2D_P(X_t)}\xi(t) \propto \frac{\delta x}{\tau_{gr}} \propto \frac{\delta x}{r^{-\gamma}}. \quad (33)$$

Assuming a scale-dependent waiting time $\tau_{gr}(r) \propto r^{-\gamma}$, with $r \equiv |X_t|$ the distance from the halo center, the corresponding scale-dependent diffusivity reads

$$D_P(X_t) = D_0 r^{2\gamma}, \quad (34)$$

where D_0 is a proportional constant. Thus diffusion is suppressed (and the waiting time enhanced) toward the halo center, leading to an increased particle density.

In spherical symmetry, the associated Fokker–Planck equation for the radial distribution $P_r(r, t)$ is

$$\frac{\partial P_r}{\partial t} = \left[\frac{\partial}{\partial r} + \frac{2}{r} \right] \left[\alpha \frac{\partial D_P}{\partial r} P_r + D_P \frac{\partial P_r}{\partial r} \right], \quad (35)$$

where α is the interpretation parameter. For the stochastic integral, the Itô interpretation yields the limit of a discrete random process as the length of the discrete intervals tends towards zero. For the Itô convention ($\alpha=1$; e.g.[21]), exact solution reads (Appendix A)

$$P_r(r, t) = \frac{(2-2\gamma)^{\frac{\gamma-2}{1-\gamma}} r^{-2\gamma}}{4\pi (D_0 t)^{\frac{3-2\gamma}{2-2\gamma}} \Gamma\left(\frac{3-2\gamma}{2-2\gamma}\right)} \exp\left(-\frac{r^{2-2\gamma}}{4(1-\gamma)^2 D_0 t}\right). \quad (36)$$

Identifying $P_r(r, t)$ with the halo density profile $\rho_r(r, t)$ yields $\rho_r \propto r^{-2\gamma}$ for a waiting time $\tau_{gr}(r) \propto r^{-\gamma}$.

The exponent γ is determined jointly by the primordial spectrum and by gravitational dynamics. In the gravity-dominated regime, the waiting time is set by the local potential, $\tau_{gr}(r) \propto \Phi_r(r)^{-1}$: deeper potentials correspond to higher local temperatures T_r , larger particle kinetic energies, and shorter residence times. In a microscopic picture, during each move, the waiting time scales as $\tau_{gr} \propto (1-P)$,

where the success probability P for a jump depends on the local temperature as $P \propto \exp(-1/T_r)$. In the high-temperature limit,

$$\tau_{gr} \propto 1-P \propto 1-\exp(-1/T_r) \propto 1/T_r \propto \Phi_r(r)^{-1}. \quad (37)$$

Equation (36) implies $\rho_r \propto r^{-2\gamma}$, so that the enclosed mass scales as $m_r \propto \rho_r r^3 \propto r^{3-2\gamma}$ and the potential as $\Phi_r(r) \propto Gm_r/r \propto r^{2-2\gamma}$. The waiting time thus also satisfies $\tau_{gr} \propto \Phi_r^{-1} \propto r^{2\gamma-2}$ from Eq. (37). Requiring consistency with $\tau_{gr} \propto r^{-\gamma}$ yields

$$2\gamma - 2 = -\gamma \quad \text{such that} \quad \gamma = 2/3, \quad (38)$$

so that the asymptotic density slope is $2\gamma = 4/3$, i.e. $\rho_r \propto r^{-4/3}$ and $\tau_{gr} \propto r^{-2/3}$. In the absence of any imprint from the initial spectrum, gravity alone therefore drives haloes toward a limiting slope of $-4/3$. For a realistic CDM spectrum, the core structure can be modified by primordial fluctuations, but universal slope $-4/3$ is expected to hold for massive haloes of characteristic mass m_h^* and on scales near r_s . Around r_s , migration is gravity-dominated, giving $\gamma = 2/3$, whereas on scales where the primordial spectrum dominates, γ is related to the effective spectral index of the initial spectrum.

Analogously to the halo mass function in Eq. (30), the effective exponent γ can take different values in two regimes: an inner region $r < r_s$, where the profile is sensitive to the primordial spectrum, and an outer region around r_s , where gravitational dynamics dominate. Adopting two exponents, γ_1 and γ_2 , for these regimes, the corresponding double- γ distribution, obtained from the single- γ solution in Eq. (36), is

$$P_r(r) = \frac{(2-2\gamma_2)^{\frac{2\gamma_1-2-\gamma_2}{1-\gamma_2}} r^{-2\gamma_1}}{4\pi (D_0 t)^{\frac{3-2\gamma_1}{2-2\gamma_2}} \Gamma\left(\frac{3-2\gamma_1}{2-2\gamma_2}\right)} \exp\left(-\frac{r^{2-2\gamma_2}}{4(1-\gamma_2)^2 D_0 t}\right). \quad (39)$$

Introducing the conventional scale radius $r_s(t)$ where the logarithmic slope of $P_r(r, t)$ is equal to -2 , we should have

$$4(1-\gamma_2)^2 D_0 t = \frac{2-2\gamma_2}{2-2\gamma_1} r_s^{2-2\gamma_2}. \quad (40)$$

Introducing a dimensionless spatial-temporal variable $x \equiv r/r_s(t)$, the resulting two-parameter radial distribution takes the form

$$P_r(x) = \frac{\alpha \beta^{-\left(\frac{1}{\alpha} + \frac{1}{\beta}\right)}}{4\pi \Gamma\left(\frac{1}{\alpha} + \frac{1}{\beta}\right)} x^{\frac{\alpha}{\beta}-2} \exp\left(-\frac{x^\alpha}{\beta}\right), \quad (41)$$

where two dimensionless parameters

$$\alpha = 2 - 2\gamma_2 \quad \text{and} \quad \beta = \frac{1 - \gamma_2}{1 - \gamma_1} \quad (42)$$

are directly related to the exponents γ_1 and γ_2 that governs the scale dependence of the waiting time $\tau_{gr}(r) \propto r^{-\gamma}$. The double- γ distribution in Eq. (41) reduces to the Einasto profile in Eq. (3) when $\alpha = 2\beta$, corresponding to $\gamma_1 = 0$, or equivalently to an initial spectrum index $n = -3$ using the approximate relation $2\gamma = 3 + n$ [5, 25], where 2γ is the density slope. In the gravity-dominated regime, $\alpha = 2\beta/3$ corresponds to $\gamma_1 = 2/3$.

5 CONCLUSIONS

We have identified a unified and general framework for describing a broad class of distributions and spectra in nonequilibrium systems, ranging from the turbulence energy spectrum to the halo mass function and density profile in cosmic structure formation. In this framework, both the turbulent spectrum and the halo statistics are interpreted as distributions of energy or mass in an appropriate “scale”

space. The evolution of these distributions is modeled as a random walk in scale space with a scale-dependent waiting time, and the corresponding probability densities are governed by Fokker–Planck equations with scale-dependent diffusivity. This stochastic description provides a common language for connecting microscopic dynamics to emergent spectra and is sufficiently general to be applied to other systems in astrophysics and beyond, where cascades or hierarchical structure in scale space play a central role.

AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS

Z.J. Xu performed the conception, data analysis, and writing.

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APPENDIX A: EXACT SOLUTION OF GENERAL FOKKER–PLANCK EQUATION

In this section, we derive exact solutions of a general d -dimensional Fokker–Planck equation in scale space x , with a power-law diffusivity $D_P(x)$ and a possible dissipation term. The equation reads

$$\frac{\partial P}{\partial t} = \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial x} + \frac{d-1}{x} \right) \left[\alpha \frac{\partial D_P}{\partial x} P + D_P \frac{\partial P}{\partial x} \right] - 2\nu x^2 P, \quad (\text{A1})$$

$$D_P(x) = D_0 x^{2\gamma} = D_0 x^g,$$

where d is the spatial dimension, α is the interpretation parameter, ν is the viscous dissipation. The associated waiting time obeys $\tau_g(x) \propto x^{-\gamma}$ with $g = 2\gamma$. We look for a similarity solution of

$$P(x, t) = \frac{A}{(D_0 t)^b x^a} \exp \left[-\frac{x^c}{f (D_0 t)^h} \right], \quad (\text{A2})$$

where the normalization constant A is fixed by $\int_0^\infty P(x) dx = 1$. Substituting Eq. (A2) into Eq. (A1) yields the algebraic constraint

$$\begin{aligned} & f^2 (D_0 t)^{2h+1} x^g (a - \alpha g) (a - g + 2 - d) \\ & + f c (D_0 t)^{h+1} x^{c+g} (c + d - 2 - 2a + g + \alpha g) \\ & - b f^2 (D_0 t)^{2h} x^2 + h f (D_0 t)^h x^{c+2} \\ & - c^2 (D_0 t) x^{2c+g} + 2 f^2 (\nu / D_0) (D_0 t)^{2h+1} x^4 = 0. \end{aligned} \quad (\text{A3})$$

For three applications, the parameters take the following forms:

(i) Stationary turbulence spectrum ($d = 1$ and $h = b = 0$):

$$a = 1 + \gamma, \quad c = 2 - \gamma, \quad \alpha = \frac{1}{2} \left(1 + \frac{1}{\gamma} \right), \quad f = (2 - \gamma) \sqrt{\frac{D_0}{2\nu}}. \quad (\text{A4})$$

(ii) Halo mass function ($d = 1$, $\nu = 0$, and $\alpha = 1/2$):

$$a = 2\alpha\gamma, \quad c = 2 - 2\gamma, \quad f = 4(1 - \gamma)^2, \quad h = 1, \quad b = \frac{1 - 2\alpha\gamma}{2(1 - \gamma)}. \quad (\text{A5})$$

(iii) Halo density profile ($d = 3$, $\nu = 0$, and $\alpha = 1$):

$$a = 2\alpha\gamma, \quad c = 2 - 2\gamma, \quad f = 4(1 - \gamma)^2, \quad h = 1, \quad b = \frac{3 - 2\alpha\gamma}{2(1 - \gamma)}. \quad (\text{A6})$$

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